

Combining deep learning and meshing techniques for automatic segmentation and 3D reconstruction of atherosclerotic carotid arteries

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In the era of personalized medicine, early and accurate prediction of individuals at high risk of severe consequences of carotid artery stenosis (CAS) which is caused by the atherosclerotic plaque deposition and progression, would allow preventive, therapeutic, or surgical measures before any of life-threatening events take place. It is therefore important to integrate machine learning techniques and computational modeling that can automatically and objectively segment and afterwards mesh the carotid arteries from image data. Among various diagnostic techniques, the US is usually initially recommended CAS diagnostic examination. The US images are used in this study as this diagnostic procedure is low-cost and present at the first level of clinical care, while its improvement in view of image processing and extracted features can be beneficial for more detailed and faster analysis of patients.

Comparing with traditional Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems where feature selection and extraction are important steps, deep learning replaces generic imaging features with processing layers that are more complex and more specific to the data. In this study, we have investigated a deep learning approach, which does not require intensity thresholds and imaging features, leading to an optimal use of information and improved prediction power. The automatic carotid artery segmentation was done using U-Net based deep convolutional network (CNN). Deep learning is combined with meshing techniques to perform 3D reconstruction of patient-specific carotid bifurcation, including extraction of atherosclerotic plaque within the arterial wall. The clinical dataset of US anonymized images was used to train and validate the U-Net CNN in automatic segmentation of carotid components (lumen, arterial wall, atherosclerotic plaque) taking into account all three arterial branches (common, internal and external carotid artery). Common classification metrics are considered for one-vs-all quantitative evaluation, including precision (P), recall (R) and F1-score. Results on the test dataset for lumen: P= 0.89, R=0.78, F1=0.83; and for wall: P=0.82 R=0.91, F1=0.85. The results of segmentation are coupled with the reconstruction software to perform a full 3D reconstruction of carotid bifurcation and generate patient-specific 3D mesh. Using the reconstruction software, it is possible to obtain 3D volume information and perform the visualization of carotid structures in different planes and from different angles.

In summary, the automatic extraction of US features related to atherosclerotic carotid artery gives the specific segmentation of individual patient-specific anatomy and can be efficiently integrated with 3D reconstruction. The obtained 3D models can be used for further computational simulations and analyses of individual patients. Integration of deep learning techniques and computer-based modelling can contribute to better risk stratification and assessment of asymptomatic patients with carotid atherosclerotic disease.

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